

***Husinska buna – proizvodnja revolucionarnog subjekta* by
Damir Arsenijević. Tuzla: Rosa-Luxemburg-Stiftung SEE
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Review

Towards the end of 2020, the 100th anniversary of the Husino rebellion was commemorated. While this anniversary was relatively covered in the media and social networks, the same cannot be said for academic and cultural circles. Several works related to the labour movement in the interwar period have been written by authors such as Denis Bećirović, current member of the Presidency of Bosnia and Herzegovina, and Salkan Užičanin, both historians. Additionally, an artistic performance was organised by the JU Museum of Eastern Bosnia Tuzla and by the author Branko Šimić. Apart from these few sporadic works, the greatest contribution has been made in the form of a shorter collection of papers titled *Husino rebellion – Production of the Revolutionary Subject*, edited by Damir Arsenijević and published by Rosa-Luxemburg-Stiftung SEE – Office in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

This shorter collection of papers contains eight works that address various topics. The main focus is placed on the historical aspect of the rebellion and its position in the chronology of the labour movement's development in Bosnia and Herzegovina and beyond. Furthermore, significant emphasis is placed on the manifestation and remembrance of Husino rebellion in later periods. The collection also includes works that are more oriented towards the question and exploration of “production of the revolutionary subject.” A particular place is dedicated to the comparison between the protests in Bosnia and Herzegovina in 2014 and the events of Husino rebellion. The book concludes with a bibliographic appendix on Husino rebellion, providing a brief historical overview of the emergence of different works and sections, thus presenting the evolution and development of this topic in historiography.

The book begins with a brief introduction by Krunoslav Stojaković, Director of the Belgrade Office of Rosa-Luxemburg-Stiftung, and the first paper is authored by Damir Arsenijević

⁶⁹⁰ The book is available as an open-source book on the website of the Rosa Luxemburg Stiftung <https://rosalux.rs/rosa-publications/husinska-buna/>.

titled *Husinska buna – proizvodnja revolucionarnog subjekta* (Husino rebellion – Production of the Revolutionary Subject). In his work, Arsenijević attempts to connect the events in Husino near Tuzla with the broader context of workers' emancipation and the events that marked the workers' struggle in that period. Furthermore, he frequently links the Husino rebellion with the events in Bosnia and Herzegovina after the aggression and the situation in which the population and the economy found themselves. Arsenijević's work is primarily based on the recollections of the main participants, Jure Kerošević and Božo Petrović. The author provides limited critical analysis of their writings and often directly quotes them.

The next three papers are very similar to one another, and their approaches are generally based on the same principles, examining the causal-events before and during the Husino rebellion as well as the significance of those events. The first paper, titled *Značaj elementa solidarnosti u husinskoj buni* (The Significance of Solidarity in Husino Rebellion) is written by Dino Šakanović. His main thesis is that the central reason for Husino rebellion is based on the solidarity of local miners from the Krka mine with the evicted individuals from state-owned apartments. According to Šakanović, these actions and solidarity are at the core of the socialist movement, and it is not surprising that miners, who were among the main initiators of the socialist movement, exhibited such behaviour. He primarily focuses on contextualising Husino rebellion within the broader labour and socialist movement, linking the commitment of workers to the following two decades until the beginning of World War II. The second paper, authored by Enes S. Omerović and titled *Mjesto husinske bune u hronologiji fenomena političkog nasilja* (The Place of Husino Rebellion in the Chronology of Political Violence Phenomena) dedicates most of its attention to the events preceding the rebellion and all the events within the workers' rights movement that led to the outbreak of the rebellion, as well as the reactions of both central and local authorities to these strikes and obstructions. In a way, Omerović's initial thesis contradicts Šakanović, as he argues that the participants in this movement belonged to a heterogeneous group whose main connection was their oppositional stance towards the state. The next article is titled *Odjeci husinske bune na ljevicu u bosni i hercegovini - uzroci povodi i posljedice* (Echoes of Husino Rebellion on the Left in Bosnia and Herzegovina – Causes, Triggers, and Consequences) and is authored by Dino Dupanović. His work focuses on the consequences of Husino rebellion on the left in Bosnia and Herzegovina and the result of conflicts among different political actors within the leftist movements. He primarily examines the conflict between the reformist-social democratic or centrist and revolutionary communist factions within the labour movement. Due to radical actions, the Communist Party soon faced a ban, and the centrists took the initiative on the left and within the labour movement. However, according to the author, there

would still be “intraparty pluralism among Bosnian Herzegovinian leftists” (p. 63.) despite the ban on communist activities and their retreat into illegality or “neutrality.”

Jasmina Husanović's work, similar to Damir Arsenijević's, primarily focuses on comparing the events related to the Husino rebellion with the current situation faced by Bosnian Herzegovinian miners. In the paper *Rudari u štrajku: stoljetna iskustva društveno-političkog rada i klasne borbe* (Miners on Strike: Centuries of Experience in Social and Political Work and Class Struggle), the emphasis is placed on the workers' struggle for their rights and their confrontation with centres of power in an attempt to improve their situation. Husanović divides her work into two parts. The first part primarily discusses the Husino rebellion and contains similar elements to Arsenijević's work, which turn these papers more into political speeches. Both authors enrich their texts with various citations from memoirs, and in both cases, the authors relatively uncritically refer to the writings of the participants of the Husino rebellion and the labour movement between the two world wars. The second part of the work is dedicated to the period after World War II, with a special focus on the events between 2014 and 2020. Husanović concludes the paper by analysing and briefly reflecting on Henry Giroux's writings regarding neoliberalism and its impact on the world.

The next two papers are culturally oriented towards the topic of the Husino rebellion. The author of the first paper is Nebojša Jovanović, and his work *Husinska buna na filmu* (Husino rebellion on Film) specifically deals with the cinematographic adaptations of the Husino rebellion during the period of Yugoslavia. Initially, the author discusses the trends within Yugoslav cinematography and the avoidance of pre-war topics by Yugoslav directors. Additionally, Jovanović analyses the film *Konjuh planinaj* (1966), which subtly evokes the Husino rebellion, although the plot takes place during World War II. The end of the paper is primarily devoted to the film *Husino Rebellion* produced by Sarajevo Television in 1980. Alongside the analysis of the *Husino Rebellion*, the author also examines other historical films produced during this period. Jovanović recognizes that earlier films could only subtly evoke certain events from Yugoslav history since the population had direct knowledge of these events from firsthand or second-hand sources. However, this was not the case with later films, as these events had already become history, and a new audience had emerged.

The next paper is titled *O klasnoj borbi i nasilju: krleža o husinskoj buni* (On Class Struggle and Violence: Krleža on the Husino rebellion) by Šejla Šehabović. In her work, the author analyses different texts written by Miroslav Krleža regarding the Husino rebellion. Similar to the works of Damir Arsenijević and Jasmina Husanović, this paper primarily deals with events in Bosnia and Herzegovina in the twenty-first century after a few pages. Šehabović compares the bloody

descriptions of violence given by Krleža, especially concerning the disembowelment of one of the leaders of the Husino rebellion, and the partial burning of the National Archive of Bosnia and Herzegovina during the protests of 2014. While Šehabović covers the comparison of other events of contemporary Bosnia to the Husino rebellion writings of Krleža, such as the burning of the Sarajevo City Hall and its restoration, the author also compares the gradual destruction of national institutions brought up by government neglect and the struggle between profit and work, which was represented in the text written by Krleža. (pp. 100–102) Nevertheless, most attention is given to the protests in 2014 and their course, as well as the results of the protests.

This collection of papers concludes with the work of Ana Vujković Šakanović titled *Istoriografija o husinskoj buni: prilog bibliografiji* (Historiography on the Husino rebellion: Contribution to the Bibliography). The author primarily analyses and presents the historical development of academic writings on the Husino rebellion. She also provides a brief overview of authors, journals, and institutions that have excelled in the study of the Husino rebellion. At the end of the paper, Vujković Šakanović presents an alphabetically arranged bibliography of sources, literature, and online resources.

Overall, this collection of papers represents an important revival of interest in a topic that has been neglected in recent times within Bosnian-Herzegovinian historiography. Additionally, this collection is significant as one of the few ways in which the centenary of the Husino rebellion has been commemorated. Although the papers within this collection do not present new historical discoveries that would shake the existing conclusions regarding the Husino rebellion, they offer a fresh perspective on this historical event. Some papers, such as the papers by Dupanović and Jovanović, have more concise themes, ideas, and conclusions presented within them. Their linear historical approach and focus on the Husino rebellion rather than on the contemporary events give them a noticeable advantage compared to other papers. That being said, other papers have a rather confusing approach to the topic, and when reading them, one gets the feeling of not reading papers about the Husino rebellion but rather about other topics.